

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Current Challenges and Innovations in Mathematics Teaching: The Birth of the "Kaalām Halin sa Kultura" Program

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 14/04/2026

Accepted: 08/05/2026

Published: 20/05/2026

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Citation: Magnate FR, Sulatra JRS (2026) Current Challenges and Innovations in Mathematics Teaching: The Birth of the "Kaalām Halin sa Kultura" Program. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 19(19): 1282-1290. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v19i19.626>

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fresanmagnate@nisu.edu.ph**Funding:** None**Competing Interests:** None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](#))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Abstract

Objectives: To identify difficulties in mathematics teaching and to develop an ethnomathematics-based, culturally relevant program for geographically isolated schools. **Methods:** The participants were eleven purposively selected mathematics teachers from elementary and secondary schools in Island School, Western Visayas, Philippines. In-depth interviews and focus group discussions, classroom observations, and document analysis were used to collect data. The data were thematically analyzed using the procedure of Braun and Clarke. **Findings:** The teachers stated that the lack of foundational skills, absenteeism, limited parental support, learning losses from modular instruction, and challenges in implementing contextualization remained a challenge. The majority of teachers reported gaps in basic numeracy skills, absences, and low parental engagement as [ongoing] barriers to continuity in learning. Furthermore, the need to review prerequisite concepts accounted for instructional delays of about 2 to 6 weeks. In response, innovations were developed, such as remedial instruction, peer tutoring, mobile learning hubs, and culturally grounded teaching. These interventions were reported to lead to significant changes in the students' engagement, participation, and conceptual understanding. The study resulted in the development of the "Kaalām Halin sa Kultura" program, a culturally responsive program that incorporates community knowledge in teaching mathematics. Results suggest that ethnomathematics-based and contextualized approaches enhance relevance, inclusiveness, and instructional effectiveness in resource-constrained settings. **Novelty:** This paper provides qualitative evidence on teachers' interactions and observations to address how a culturally responsive-ethnomathematics-based approach can narrow equity gaps and increase the relevance of instructional practices. It describes a local ethnomathematics program drawing ideas from teachers' innovations in geographically isolated schools across the Philippines.

Keywords: Mathematics education; Ethnomathematics; Culturally relevant teaching; Learning gaps; Teacher innovation

1 Introduction

Mathematics is a crucial component of the Philippine Educational System; hence, the Department of Education (DepEd) emphasized that learning content should be contextualized, localized, and indigenized to make instruction relevant to what is significant in the cultural backgrounds and life experiences of our learners⁽¹⁾. The policy turns towards meaningful learning by bringing community realities into classroom instruction. However, despite such mandates for cultural relevance in mathematics education, common measures of culturally responsive pedagogy are inconsistent in practice, and fewer resources with limited training on contextual materials exist, especially in geographically isolated and disadvantaged settings.

Traditionally, the teaching of mathematics has emphasized formal and abstract representations overriding the rich mathematical knowledge embedded in local cultural practices. Cultural activities such as traditional crafts, architectural designs and indigenous systems contain important mathematical ideas, as shown by Alangui⁽²⁾, Prahmana and D'Ambrosio⁽³⁾, Fauzi et al.⁽⁴⁾ and Primaniarta and de Mattos⁽⁵⁾. Furthermore, Meaney et al.⁽⁶⁾ emphasize cultural symmetry in the teaching. According to Mania and Alam⁽⁷⁾, ethnomathematics has motivational value in classroom practice. These studies focus only on documenting mathematical concepts embedded in indigenous traditions, crafts, and cultural activities, but have not examined how these concepts can be utilized to create or develop a program integrated in the formal mathematics classroom that may address to the challenges, such as learning gaps and weak foundational skills. Although Batiibwe⁽⁸⁾ and Asare⁽⁹⁾ recognize the pedagogical value of ethnomathematics, there are still limited studies describing the development of localized, teacher-driven programs that integrate cultural knowledge into mathematics teaching and learning. Beyond this hiatus, the recent shifts in the delivery of education, particularly during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, have added to the challenges of mathematics education. While students may have passed by virtue of the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), this does not guarantee that they learned the basics. The transition from modular and blended learning modalities has led to learning loss, less interest in students towards their lessons, and increasing heterogeneity among learners' domains. Thus, the reported high level of academic achievement among secondary school students does not match their actual understanding in a manner that allows effective delivery of the curriculum by teachers. To address these gaps, the study was pursued, which aims to: (1) identify the existing challenges of mathematics teachers in geographically isolated schools; (2) explore the innovations and strategies used to overcome the challenges; and (3) narrate the development of the "*Kaalang Halin sa Kultura*" program as a culturally responsive intervention to enhance mathematics teaching and learning.

These persistent challenges indicate a need for more context-sensitive and innovative approaches to meet the dual challenge of learning gaps and the relevance of mathematics instruction. This led to the creation of the program "*Kaalang Halin sa Kultura*" as a way of linking formal mathematics and cultural knowledge by using pedagogical integration. The program consists of 5 phases combining research and extension initiatives. Phase 1 focuses on determining teachers' knowledge, skills, and processes in integrating ethnomathematics into the mathematics curriculum, accompanied by a seminar on ethnomathematics. Phase 2 involved the development of culturally relevant instructional materials and teacher training workshops on integrating culture into mathematics instruction. Phase 3 centered on the development of a web-based learning management system (LMS) that serves as a repository of culturally relevant innovations in mathematics education, together with workshops on action research development using culturally relevant instructional materials. Phase 4 included the implementation, workshop, and evaluation of culture-based mathematics learning plans, instructional aids, and activities aligned with teachers' grade-level assignments. Finally, Phase 5 focused on the evaluation of the entire program and consultation sessions on the utilization of the LMS containing culture-based mathematics resources. The program is based on ethnomathematics and culturally relevant teaching to increase students' understanding, engagement, and appreciation of mathematics by connecting abstract ideas to familiar cultural experiences. This approach is in line with the vision of DepEd for inclusive and culturally responsive education⁽²⁾,⁽¹⁰⁾,⁽¹¹⁾. This also speaks to what Alangui⁽²⁾ raises as the issues on de contextualization and colonization of knowledge. At present, the "*Kaalang Halin sa Kultura*" program is in its initial implementation and evaluation stage. Therefore, the findings of this study should be interpreted as preliminary qualitative evidence of the program's potential contribution to culturally responsive mathematics education in geographically isolated settings.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

Qualitative descriptive research of Sandelowski⁽¹²⁾ was adopted to systematically document the challenges and teaching innovations observed and experienced by mathematics teachers both at the elementary and secondary levels. The research is grounded in a constructivist epistemology guided by an interpretivist perspective, to understand the meanings and perspectives that individuals assign to their experiences⁽¹³⁾,⁽¹⁴⁾. The design allows for a comprehensive and low-inference description

of real-world educational phenomena, making it appropriate for capturing context-specific challenges and innovations in geographically isolated settings.

2.2 Informants

This involved the eleven (11) teachers selected using the purposeful sampling technique⁽¹⁵⁾. To select the informants, the following criteria were considered: a) The informant must be a permanent teacher in a public elementary or secondary school in Gigantes Island, Carles, Iloilo, Philippines, teaching mathematics, and b) involvement in contextualized or localized teaching. The sample included elementary and secondary teachers to ensure representation across grade levels and instructional settings. Data saturation was reached when no new themes were identified in the analysis, suggesting an adequate sample size for qualitative research⁽¹⁶⁾.

2.3 Data Collection

Data was collected from interviews, classroom observations, and document analysis, an original copy of which is securely hosted by the researchers, but not freely available due to potential ethical considerations; it can be supplied on reasonable request. This approach is aligned with existing qualitative research standards, which emphasize trustworthiness of data, rather than open data set repositories. Data triangulation was employed through focus group discussions with the participants to avoid biased interpretation of the meaning of their statements. Classroom observations were conducted through a structured observation guide with a focus on instructional strategies, student engagement, and integration of contextualized practices; classroom observation to observe instructional practices and learners' engagement; and checking relevant DepEd memoranda. Data were collected via interviews and focus group discussions from participants in mixed English, Filipino (Tagalog), and Hiligaynon (Local Dialect) to allow them the freedom of expression. The interviews and FGDs were audio-recorded with permission from the participants and transcribed verbatim for analysis.

2.4 Data Analysis

Data were analyzed with thematic analysis constructed according to Braun and Clarke⁽¹⁷⁾. We inductively coded the field notes and transcripts for common themes where we found challenges, innovations, and connections to ethnomathematics within classroom practice. Clusters of codes were developed, which allowed for a comparison between the elementary and secondary levels, to illustrate patterns in responses and coding that emerged with both levels.

2.5 Ethical Considerations

All participants provided informed consent. However, data confidentiality and anonymity were preserved. The current research was reviewed and approved according to standard ethical regulations for qualitative research at each participating institution.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Current Challenges of Teachers in Mathematics Education

Today, mathematics teachers face challenges in teaching and learning mathematics. These are a lack of fundamental skills, high absenteeism, and low parental support, learning loss from the pandemic, especially compliance with MELC and use of contextualization, localization, and indigenization. The challenges are systemic, exposing structural and instructional weaknesses that cannot be fixed by classroom strategies alone. The systemic support, flexible policies, and sufficient provision of resources are vital to enable the implementation of DepEd initiatives on localization and contextualization, but what often matters most is the ingenuity of our teachers. The hope of instituting truly meaningful, culturally sensitive, and equitable mathematics education in the Philippines will continue to remain an unattained aspiration for many of its students if these challenges are not addressed. The learning environments post-pandemic have exacerbated the fundamental learning gaps, particularly in mathematics⁽¹⁸⁾. Ikram et al.⁽¹⁹⁾ pointed out that the interruption of structured learning contexts affects students' cognitive growth and problem-solving abilities, emphasizing the need for responsive teaching methods. The findings of this study underscore that the challenges seen in geographically isolated Philippine contexts are reflected in broader international trends in education recovery.

Lack of foundational skills. Teachers from elementary and secondary schools encountered a shared challenge: students came back to class with grades that suggested proficiency, but they were missing the fundamental skills necessary to participate

effectively in their current math lessons. The teachers observed that a significant challenge they faced during in-person classes was the students' lack of foundational skills in mathematics. This encompasses challenges in identifying numbers and letters, along with the wrong writing of them. The absence of essential skills makes it difficult for students to advance in more complex mathematical ideas, creating challenges for teachers in successfully implementing the curriculum. Foundational gaps are not only academic but also influenced by limited instructional support and resource constraints. For instance, Alashwal and Barham⁽²⁰⁾ found that gaps in foundational mathematical understanding significantly hinder students' ability to engage in higher-order problem-solving tasks. Similarly, Asare⁽⁹⁾ demonstrated that students exposed to culturally responsive and ethnomathematics-based instruction showed improved conceptual understanding compared to those taught using traditional methods. Teacher Lory shared: "Our lower section, sir, is still unable to recognize numbers, and the letters are all written incorrectly. Their mental capacity appears to be extremely low." Moreover, Teacher Queene also shared "...first thing I notice is that they do not know how to read. We really started in the basic, from letter sounding and syllables". This deficiency in foundational knowledge could be traced back to earlier grades, where fundamental math operations were not mastered. As teacher Shan mentioned, "...the problem is the foundation of the students from their elementary years: during grades 4, 5, and 6, they are expected to master basic operations because the moment they stepped into high school, grade 7, they will be introduced to advanced mathematics." It shows the need to revisit elementary-level topics before progressing to the current grade's curriculum. Such setbacks in foundational knowledge often delay the pace of math instruction. He added, "...because they lack a foundation, you must return to earlier topics and more often to the elementary level of instruction before moving on to your actual lesson. As a result, our lessons are delayed because we must go back before moving forward. As a result, our lessons are delayed because we must go back before moving forward..."

These suggest that learning gaps are influenced not only by content difficulty but also by disruptions in prior learning experiences, unequal access to instructional support, and variations in learners' socio-cultural contexts. Learning disruptions affected students in marginalized communities, resulting in persistent gaps in numeracy and comprehension, which may prompt the country to rethink the current educational systems to align it in international assessment standards, which not only measure knowledge but also the ability of the learners to apply it in reality⁽¹⁶⁾.

High absenteeism rates and limited parental involvement. Absenteeism and limited parental involvement were also mentioned by teachers as barriers to learning. Across both levels, students were frequently absent, often due to economic or family-related reasons. These observations emphasize the critical role of home support and consistent attendance in academic achievement since parental involvement contributes significantly to uneven learning outcomes across socio-economic contexts⁽¹⁶⁾. Furthermore, Costa⁽²¹⁾ highlights that educational inequalities are often intensified in marginalized communities where institutional and family-level support systems are limited. Teacher Herlyn reflected, "Absenteeism—this is the number one reason why they are like that." Others noted how modular learning during the pandemic placed too much responsibility on parents, many of whom lacked the time or capability to assist their children. Teacher Rob pointed out that "Parental involvement varies... some students just don't have the support at home." These situations made it difficult for students to maintain learning continuity. While DepEd encourages school-community partnerships through its School-Based Management system, these accounts show that teachers are left to compensate for gaps in home support. The need to strengthen parental orientation and community-based interventions is clear, especially if education is to become a shared responsibility. Absenteeism and weak parental engagement should not be viewed solely as individual learner concerns but as systemic challenges connected to poverty, geographic isolation, and unequal access to educational resources, which result in being vulnerable to disengagement and interrupted learning due to socio-economic instability and limited educational support systems⁽²²⁾.

Learning losses stemming from the modular learning. The prolonged use of modular and remote learning was seen by teachers as having long-term effects. Many students returned to school lacking interest, discipline, and basic understanding of math. Remote and modular learning modalities often fail to sustain student engagement and deep learning, particularly in mathematics⁽¹⁷⁾. Moreover, Li et al.⁽¹⁶⁾ emphasize that abrupt transitions in instructional delivery led to increased variability in learner competencies. Teachers described the two years of modular instruction as ineffective in ensuring meaningful learning. Teacher Lyka shared, "That 2 years of modular was a waste of time. No learnings at all." Teachers observed that students faced challenges with the sudden shift to online and modular learning, which affected their engagement and performance in mathematics. Teacher Topi shared "...the transitions on the learning of the students since two years that we did not have face to face, they depended on modular, they have low interest and learnings to the subject specially on math, it is hard for them since they have no proper learnings to assist or to help them so there were times that some learners cannot understand, some are very slow." A lot of students struggled to adjust to this new way of learning, particularly with subjects like mathematics that typically benefit from face-to-face interaction and practical experience. Teachers expressed that the curriculum presented intricate subjects at the beginning of the academic year, leading to feelings of overwhelm among students. Teacher Judy narrated "on our first week, that was still a blended week, you can see in the expression of the learners that they are somewhat, "culture shocked" to their

subject, *General Mathematics*. It was not basic and already have complicated topics so it was hard for them, that they will start on complicated topics already. In lower grade, it was different because it is still not that complicated. But with this, they are struggling to their topics. There are some that are really striving to understand it...” This simply shows that teachers are confronted with the challenge of balancing curriculum compliance and learner recovery when there are uneven learning competencies. This adds to the need to rethink the curriculum to be flexible in the pacing mechanism, considering the country’s historical, social, political, cultural, and institutional contexts⁽¹⁸⁾. In doing so, this not only aligns with the actual political and policy agenda of the country, but also with the PISA framework, which is considered a comparative benchmark for countries.

Compliance with the MELC. Falling behind the MELCs was another shared concern. Teachers frequently described being “off track” because of the need to constantly go back to basics. Teacher Anne said, “*I am still in what, week 4. We should be at least in the 10th week lesson.*” The delays range from 2 to 6 weeks depending on the learner’s capacity. Mixed-ability classrooms complicated the situation, with some learners requiring more time while others waited. Teacher Sheila added, “*There are topics we cannot cover because of our slow pacing.*” This difficulty in meeting curriculum pacing requirements suggests that rigid curriculum structures often conflict with the realities of diverse learner readiness⁽²⁰⁾.

Implementing contextualization, localization, and indigenization. The challenge of implementing contextualization, localization, and indigenization strategies was repeatedly brought up. Although teachers value these approaches, many find it difficult to apply them across all topics, especially abstract math concepts. This challenge reflects a well-documented gap between policy and practice in culturally responsive education. Batiibwe⁽⁸⁾ emphasizes that while ethnomathematics is widely recognized for its pedagogical value, teachers often lack concrete frameworks and training for implementation. In addition, Asare⁽⁹⁾ found that effective ethnomathematics integration requires structured instructional support and contextualized materials. Teacher Shan reflected, “*It is very difficult for us, especially in solving functions, to apply localization or indigenization.*” Others tried to integrate native language and culturally relevant examples but struggled due to the lack of training or resources. Teacher Ken remarked, “*Localization is not just about materials... it’s about making examples they can relate to.*” This demonstrates teachers’ awareness of what contextualization should achieve but also exposes the limitations they face in practice. DepEd Orders^{(1), (23)} call for every region to adapt the curriculum based on local contexts. However, without concrete exemplars, teacher training, and access to indigenous knowledge systems, this mandate remains aspirational for many educators.

3.2 Current innovations implemented by teachers and schools

In response to learning disruptions, mathematics teachers in elementary and secondary schools have implemented various innovative strategies to improve teaching and learning outcomes. These approaches reflect their adaptability and commitment to addressing students’ needs. Key practices include remedial strategies, peer tutoring, culturally grounded instruction, and enhanced resource access, all aimed at bridging learning gaps and engaging diverse learners. These innovations align with DepEd’s goals of localization, contextualization, and indigenization of the curriculum. To ensure the sustainability and enhancement of these efforts, continued professional development, policy flexibility, and community engagement are essential for long-term educational recovery and transformation. Learner-centered and culturally grounded approaches instructional strategies that are responsive to learners’ needs significantly enhance engagement and problem-solving abilities, and contribute to addressing educational disruptions^{(8), (21)}.

Remediation and Individualized Instruction. One of the most commonly practiced innovations at both levels is the use of remedial and individualized instruction to meet students’ diverse learning needs. Teachers reported that revisiting foundational skills and adjusting task complexity according to each learner’s capacity made the transition back to face-to-face learning smoother. For struggling learners, particularly those who have difficulty with counting, number recognition, or basic operations, teachers implemented accommodations. For example, they focused on counting only up to 10 or 50, while providing more advanced exercises for faster learners. Teacher Anne noted, “*I made them start with 1 to 10, especially those from the lower section.*” Teachers made themselves available during vacant periods and invited students to seek help without hesitation. Teacher Sheila explained, “*I always told them that if ever they cannot understand their lesson, they can always tap me or any teacher to explain and remediate with their gaps.*” These strategies reflect a deep understanding of learner variability and support DepEd’s advocacy for inclusive education, reinforcing the mandate to contextualize instruction based on actual learning readiness.

Peer Tutoring and Collaborative Learning. To overcome the difficulty of large class sizes and mixed-ability groups, both elementary and secondary teachers-initiated peer tutoring systems, where advanced or fast learners were assigned to help their struggling classmates. In elementary schools, teachers described organizing pair or small-group work where students could support one another. In high school, peer tutoring was more structured, with students chosen by teachers to assist others. “*We select students that will teach their peers because we cannot cater to all the students at the same time,*” teacher Ken explained. This innovation not only strengthened the learners’ sense of responsibility but also encouraged a collaborative environment. It cultivated a classroom culture where learning was communal rather than competitive.

Mobile Learning Hubs and Learning Resource Expansion. A school-wide innovation at the secondary level was the establishment of Mobile Learning Hubs—mobile library units that provided access to reading and math materials, technology, and tutoring support for students with limited resources. Teacher Judy described, “*This mobile learning hub caters learners in different subjects. It serves as their moving library.*” These hubs became vital, especially in areas where students lacked internet or printed modules during the pandemic. Teacher Shan added “*...in the ML hub, we do not only cater for queries but also have their library. The ML Hub caters Filipino, Mathematics, English, and Science subjects, there’s a library as well as we put a computer and there is a teacher stationed there to facilitate...*”. Though more common in high schools, similar resource expansion efforts were noted in elementary schools through the use of learning corners, rotating activity stations, and community learning spaces. These initiatives demonstrate how schools are attempting to decentralize access to learning materials and create more inclusive educational environments, echoing DepEd’s push for alternative learning strategies and multi-modal resource delivery.

Monthly Numeracy Assessments and Progress Monitoring. To monitor learner progress and evaluate the effectiveness of interventions, some schools introduced monthly numeracy assessments. These tests identified proficiency levels, such as proficient, frustrated, or non-numerate, and guided remediation and instructional planning. As teacher Topi explained, “*We have monthly numeracy tests... to identify their level. It helps track who needs more support.*” This data-driven method gave teachers the tools they needed to make smart choices, set realistic targets, and celebrate even small improvements.

Use of Vernacular and Cultural Integration. Teachers also incorporated vernacular language and culturally grounded materials to improve comprehension and make lessons more relatable. In both elementary and secondary schools, teachers observed that students responded more positively when instructions and examples were delivered in their native language, particularly Hiligaynon. Teacher Rob explained, “*We need to make our level of teaching easier to understand... if we need to use vernacular, we use it.*” Using local measurement systems, traditional games, or patterns from weaving and fishing nets to teach mathematical concepts is also an ethnomathematics practice.

3.3 “Kaalam Halin sa Kultura” Program: Its Birth

The phrase “*Kaalam Halin sa Kultura*” is a Filipino dialect that means *Knowledge from the Culture*. The purpose of this program is to strengthen mathematics teaching and learning in the Island community by equipping teachers with strategies and tools to develop mathematics learning plans and aids that reflect the cultural diversity of their students, promoting inclusivity and engagement in the learning process. This initiative was conceptualized to develop an Ethnomathematics Program within the island communities, encompassing multiple dimensions: Cognitive, Conceptual, Educational, Epistemological, Historical, and Political⁽¹⁹⁾. This program is the result of many complementary phases of research and extension (Table 1).

The extension initiatives are integral to the “*Kaalam Halin sa Kultura*” program, which seeks to develop a Web-Based Learning Management System (LMS) for Mathematics learning plans, materials, and activities informed by cultural relevance. The LMS was designed for offline use, making it suitable for island communities with limited connectivity.

Moreover, the “*Kaalam Halin sa Kultura*” (Knowledge from the Culture) Program is also proposed as a culturally-adapted educational modality intervention that responds to these prevalent issues while complementing adaptations already established by teachers. Located within the rich tradition of ethnomathematics, our program seeks to connect curriculum standards and community knowledge systems that would work toward making mathematics implementation more equitable, practical, and contextually appropriate for students in Western Visayas, Philippines, and beyond. Batiibwe⁽⁸⁾, ethnomathematics plays a critical role in bridging cultural knowledge and formal mathematical instruction. Additionally, Asare⁽⁹⁾ provides empirical evidence that ethnomathematics-based instruction significantly improves students’ attitudes, participation, and cultural connectedness.

The program aims to address the call of the teachers who seek assistance in appropriately contextualizing, localizing, and indigenizing their lessons so students can learn in ways that are informed by their cultural backgrounds⁽¹²⁾. Also, through this program, it aims to utilize the culture of the country, specifically in the fishery community, to contextualize and interest mathematical ideas among students. Arguably, the program symbolizes the need for contextualized education to be able to address this issue by localizing the lessons and indigenizing class discussion materials with the use of real-life culturally relevant examples, which deepens appreciation of mathematics as a tool in problem solving through everyday life.

4 Conclusion

The “*Kaalam Halin sa Kultura*” program exemplifies a culturally rooted response to the long-standing challenges of math education in a geographically isolated context. The program integrates ethnomathematics into classroom practice, tackling pressing issues of learning loss, poor foundational skills and engagement, and the disconnect between formal mathematics in classrooms and what students experience in their own lives. Grounded in culturally responsive pedagogy, it gives teachers

Table 1. Phases in the Development through Research and Extension

Phase	Research Initiative	Extension Initiative
1	Determine teachers' knowledge, skills, and processes on integrating ethnomathematics in the mathematics curriculum	Conducted a Seminar on Ethnomathematics
2	Developed culturally-relevant instructional materials in mathematics	Train teachers to integrate culture into the mathematics curriculum through a training workshop
3	Development of a web application that will serve as a data bank for all culturally related innovations for mathematics education	Training Workshop on the Development of Action Research Proposal through Culturally Relevant Instructional Materials in Mathematics
4	Implementation of each innovation corresponding to each grade level of teacher's assignment.	Workshop and Evaluation of Mathematics Learning Plans, Aids, and Activities that are Culture-Based for Integration in Web-Based Learning Management System (LMS)
5	Evaluation of the entire program which also includes feedback.	Training and Consultation Session on the Utilization of Web-Based Learning Management System (LMS) with Mathematics Learning Plans, Aids, and Activities that are Culture-Based

not only flexible and context-sensitive strategies based on the complex realities but also the ability to implement practices that promote inclusive instructional strategies, enhance comprehension, and create significant learning experiences for students^{(24), (25), (26)}.

The results of this study show that bottom-up teacher effort-focused solutions, such as remediation, peer tutoring, vernacular language use, and example drawings from the culture, address many learning gaps. It leverages these grassroots practices through a structured yet flexible framework coherent with education policies in the country, which include DepEd Orders^{(1), (22)} and is aligned with the Philippine Education's goals relative to BEDP 2030⁽²⁷⁾. It thus implements contextualization, localization, and indigenization in a practical and sustainable.

Furthermore, the program helps rethink mathematics education by applying culture as a purposeful base in curriculum, instruction, and assessment⁽²⁸⁾. It helps to validate the inherent worth of indigenous knowledge systems and also pushes back against the imperialism of Western mathematical perspectives, while advancing equity and inclusion in education⁽¹¹⁾. Local practices such as "Pambubo" are examples of how common household activities represent a number of mathematical concepts and therefore make learning more contextually meaningful and easier for students⁽²⁹⁾. At this moment, the initial phase of implementing the "Kaalang Halin sa Kultura" program is on its testing stage in real classroom settings to assess its effects on changing teachers' practices and student learning outcomes. Initial feedback from some of the teachers involved suggests that it has enabled new levels of learner engagement and contextual understanding, although this is currently under systematic evaluation.

Despite these worthwhile contributions, the study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the findings are primarily based on teachers' experiences, observations, and interpretations, which may introduce subjectivity in the analysis. Second, the study involved a relatively small sample of teachers from geographically isolated schools within one specific area, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other educational contexts. Third, the study focused more on teacher perspectives and did not include quantitative measures of the program's impact on students' academic performance, such as achievement scores, numeracy proficiency levels, retention rates, or standardized assessment results.

Lastly, the "Kaalang Halin sa Kultura" is a promising approach to enhancing mathematics education by integrating curriculum requirements with cultural knowledge systems. Although our current results offer robust qualitative evidence for its significance / possible efficacy, further empirical validation (quantitative and large-scale implementation studies) is needed to make more generalizable claims on impact. This emphasizes the need to empower teachers as a powerful agent of change and centers on the potential of culturally responsive teaching in enriching student participation, comprehension, and further learning effectively. Future studies may employ mixed-methods, quantitative, or longitudinal research designs to examine the effectiveness of the program using more objective and measurable indicators of student learning outcomes. Further investigations may also explore the sustainability, scalability, and adaptability of the program across different regions, learner characteristics, and educational settings to provide broader empirical validation of culturally responsive and ethnomathematics-based instructional approaches.

5 Declarations

Acknowledgement: We are grateful to the teachers who participated in this study and to the school heads who allowed us to conduct the study in their schools.

Funding: The work was funded by Northern Iloilo State University (BOT Resolution No. 80 s, 2021).

Data availability: The data has not been made publicly available to protect participants' privacy. Moreover, the participants do not give written consent to publicly share their data. Nonetheless, the authors are willing to provide more detailed information from the interviews and observations.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no competing interests.

Acknowledgements: The authors are grateful to the teachers who participated in this study and to the school heads who allowed us to conduct the study in their schools.

Funding: The work was funded by Northern Iloilo State University (BOT Resolution No. 80 s, 2021).

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